

ENHANCING IMAGINATION THROUGH ANIMATIONS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING THE SCIENCES OF ENGINEERING GRAPHICS

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ABSTRACT The development of creative students in all aspects is our highest goal. One of the most important aspects of working with creative students is preparing them for the Olympics.

Key words: Drawing geometry, imagination, creativity, potential, creative problem, animation, Caspian skill.

In the current issue, we will consider some issues from drawing geometry to prepare students for Olympiads. These problems allow students to easily understand the problems of drawing geometry. In preparing students for science olympiads, problems of drawing geometry are presented in the form of animation, students have the opportunity to easily understand and master the problem.

Issue 1. Find the missing (A') projection of the point A located 20mm from the given plane P (P_v, P_H)

Solution: We choose an arbitrary point N in the plane P in the given general situation. From the selected point N to the plane P , straight lines are drawn from traces H and V . The extracted straight lines are stopped at an arbitrary point T , and the NT points come to the cross-section state, and the real size of this NT cross-section is determined. Then, a distance of 20 mm is measured from the point N' to the actual size of the NT section found. A measured distance of 20 mm gives us the point M_0 . Going back from the point M_0 to the intersection T_0, T' , we get the point M' . We determine the point M'' in the projection V from the point M' through the projection connection. Then we pass the special lines h''

from the point M'' and h' from the point M' , and determine the points V trace $1''$ and H trace $1'$ of the traces of these lines. Then we transfer the projection Qv of the new plane Q through this point to Pv . The transferred plane Qv intersects the axis OX and forms the point Qx . We determine QH by drawing $\parallel$ from the point Qx to the plane Φ . Then the missing projection of the given point A is found in the problem. For this, we assume that the point A lies in the plane Q and we get the answer to the problem.

Due to the complexity of drawing geometry, a student may struggle to understand. In explaining these issues, the solution presented in the animation makes it easy for the imagination to be quickly assimilated and easily mastered.

Problem 2 Let a straight line be drawn from the point C of the line AB perpendicular to this line and parallel to the given plane P

To solve the problem, two planes are drawn through point C on the given line AB . One of the planes, for example, Q AB must be perpendicular to the line ($Q \perp AB$), and the other plane T must be parallel to the given plane P . The line of intersection of planes Q and T is the answer to the problem.

1. From the point C , the horizontal of the plane Q shown above CE is passed ($C'E'' \parallel OX, C'E' \perp A'B'$) and frontal CF ($C'F' \parallel OX, C''F'' \perp A''B''$).
2. From point C , the second (parallel to P) plane T is horizontal $C1$ ($C''1'' \parallel OX, C'1' \parallel PH$) and front $C2$ ($C'2' \parallel OX, C''2'' \parallel Pv$) are transferred.
3. Find the common point (other than C) for the resulting triangle CEF and $1C2$ planes. For this, the intersection point D of the line EF ($E''F'', E'F'$) with the

intersection of the planes P is the answer to the problem.

Working with creative students is one of the priorities of the modern educational process. Caring for creative students today is to create a foundation for the development of science, culture, and social life in the future. In this regard, measures to support creative students in various fields of activity are increasing.

The modern economy is increasingly in need of specialists with deep knowledge and innovative ability, therefore identification and development of young talents based on the best historical experience and the most successful modern models is a necessary element of the development of Uzbekistan.

In our country, at the level of cooperation, measures are being taken to support young people in innovative project activities and involve students and young professionals in solving the current problems of the country's development

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